

Table 1. Insect transmission tests of gall dwarf isolate from insect. Thailand.

Natural insects collected from Uthai Thani, Thailand by H. Inoue in August 1979	Inoculated to healthy plants (infection) ^a	Symptom		Transmission tested by	Infection ^a	Symptom
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	2 of 8	Gall dwarf	Back Transmission	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0 of 32	—
				<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	3 of 67	Gall dwarf
				<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	1 of 7	Gall dwarf

Result of serial daily transmission by a single insect.^b

Insect	Insect no.	Result at given no. of transfers																				
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	
<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	2	○	○	○	W	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	●	D
	41	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
	67	○	○	W	⊙	○	W	○	●	●	●	●	○	D								
Acquisition feeding for 2 days and inoculation feeding for 1 day. Total insects used = 67																						
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	4	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	W	○	●	W	●	●	●	●	●	○	●	E	
	Acquisition feeding for 1 day and inoculation feeding for 1 day. Total insects used = 7																					

^aNumber of plants showing infection with positive results and total no. of plants tested.

^b● transmitted the disease.

○ failed to transmit.

W seedling wilted.

D insect died.

● insect molted and transmitted the disease.

⊙ insect molted but failed to transmit the disease.

E insect escaped.

Table 2. Insect transmission tests of gall dwarf isolate from the plant. Thailand.

Severely stunted and dark-green rice plants resembling those with rice dwarf virus disease collected from Uthai Thani, Thailand, by T. Omura in August 1979	Transmission tested by	Infection ^a	Symptom		Transmission tested by	Infection	Symptom
	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	3 of 43	Rice ragged stunt virus	Back Transmission	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0 of 41	—
	<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	1 of 44	Gall dwarf		<i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	5 of 40	Gall dwarf
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	0 of 47	—		<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	0 of 53	—	

Result of back-transmission by single insect, *Recilia dorsalis*.

Insect no.	Result ^b at given no. of transfers				
	1	2	3	4	5
10	○	○	●	○	D
13	○	W	○	○	●
29	○	○	○	●	D
32	○	○	●	○	○
38	○	●	●	●	●

^a Number of plants showing infection with positive results and total no. of plants tested.

^b Acquisition feeding for 1 day, inoculation period for 7 days and inoculation feeding for 2 days (1 insect/plant). Total insects used = 40. For explanation of symbols, see footnote to Table 1.

Observations on rice gall dwarf, a new virus disease

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Galls found on the leaves and leaf sheaths of dark-green, dwarf rice plants in fields at Uthai Thani, Thailand, in August 1979 were presumed to be of a new virus disease that was named rice gall dwarf.

Leafhoppers *Nephotettix nigropictus* at early instars were used in a transmission test. After 1 day of acquisition feeding the insects were serially transferred to rice test seedlings 2 times/week. The insects transmitted rice gall dwarf in a persistent manner; of the 16 tested,

4 transmitted the disease. The minimum latent period of the virus in the insects was 14 days; the maximum, 20 days.

Seedling inoculation at the first- to third-leaf stages showed the following symptoms: dwarfing, appearance of galls along the leaf blades and sheaths, dark-green discoloration, twisting of the leaf tips, reduction in number of tillers, and death of the entire plant at later infection stages. Dwarfing and discoloration are the characteristic symptoms of the

diseased plants in the field, except those infected at later growth stages. No yellowish-white specks — the typical symptom of rice dwarf virus (RDV) disease — were observed on the leaf blades.

The dwarfing, caused by incomplete emergence of the younger leaves, was particularly conspicuous in the plants inoculated at earlier growth stages.

The galls or vein-swellings appeared on the undersurface of the leaf blades and on the upper parts of the leaf sheaths.

The galls were light green and rather translucent at first, but later became brownish. They were more abundant in early infected plants, some of whose leaves had more than 10 galls. The galls varied from 0.4 to 0.5 mm in width and 0.4 to 8 mm in length.

The discoloration of infected plants was another characteristic symptom. Infected hills were easily recognized by their dark-green color in the field and in the transmission test.

Another minor symptom was the twisting of the tips of newly developed leaves — supposedly because of an alternating, uneven growth of the leaf blades on both sides of the midrib.

The plant's leaf tip began to dry; eventually, the entire plant dried and died.

Spherical particles about 65 nm in diameter (vs 70 nm in RDV), were always observed in the leaf-dip preparations of gall dwarf-infected tissues (photo 1). They were more abundant in the preparations from galls than in those from nongall leaf tissues. The particles had a capsid-like structure. Ultrathin sections showed virus particles in the phloem cells of the diseased plant (photo 2).

The clumping technique was used in an immunoelectron microscopic test to study the serological relationship of the particles with RDV. Particles that consistently appeared in preparations of grids with RDV and RDV antiserum were many and clumped while those observed on the grids with specimens infected with rice gall dwarf disease and RDV antiserum were few and dispersed.

Among the rice virus diseases, rice black-streaked dwarf and rice ragged stunt have a symptomatology similar to

1. Electron micrograph showing virus particles in a dip preparation from the sample infected with rice gall dwarf disease.

2. Electron micrograph showing virus particles in a phloem cell of a rice plant infected with rice gall dwarf disease.

that of rice gall dwarf disease. But rice gall dwarf induces the formation of numerous small galls; the other diseases produce a few elongated swellings of the veins. It is difficult to distinguish rice gall dwarf disease from rice ragged stunt in the field. Plants with rice gall dwarf disease, however, have no ragged leaf blades and their leaves become dark green unlike those of plants infected with ragged stunt.

The causal agent of rice gall disease is presumably a virus with spherical

particles about 65 nm in diameter, capsid-like in structure. Three rice viruses are reported among the plant reovirus group — RDV, rice black-streaked dwarf virus, and rice ragged stunt. Only the virus particles of RDV have a capsid-like structure. But immunoelectron microscopic examination revealed that the particles associated with rice gall dwarf disease are not serologically related to RDV, suggesting that rice gall dwarf is a new virus disease. ■

Chlorotic streak, a new virus disease of rice

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Since 1978, we have observed a new virus disease of rice on the CRRI farm and in farmers' fields surrounding Cuttack. In the field the disease occurs in patches (Fig. 1) ranging in size from about 1 to 10 m². Its severity decreases from the center to the outer edges of the affected patch. The diseased plants in the center are much more severely damaged than those on the edge, indicating that a slow-moving agent spreads the disease.

In artificially inoculated plants, the symptoms were stunted plant growth (Fig. 2), chlorotic streaking, striping, or mottling (Fig. 3) of the newly emerging leaves; difficult emergence of leaves and panicles; and brown discoloration and grain sterility. Chlorotic streaks also appeared on the leaf sheaths. Other

1. Diseased patch of rice chlorotic streak in farmers' field. The circle represents the diseased patch.

symptoms observed occasionally were twisting, curling, crinkling, blunt edges, wavy margin, ragging, tearing, raised blisters, rough surface, and dark green color of the leaves; swelling and irregular